

**Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology as a Predictor of Quality
Science Education**

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Abstract

The study investigated whether students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) is a predictor of quality of science education in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE). Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study. The students' scores in Basic Science and Technology in BECE for 2010/2011, 2011/2012, 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 academic sessions and their corresponding science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics results in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) for 2013/2014, 2014/2015, 2015/2016 and 2016/2017 academic sessions respectively were used. Regression analysis was used to answer the research questions as well as to test the null hypotheses. The findings revealed that students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology is a moderate predictor of quality education in Biology ($\beta = 19.2\%$). The results also showed that the achievement of students in Basic Science and Technology significantly predicts their quality of education in Chemistry ($\beta = 15.7\%$). It was also found that the achievement of students in Basic Science and Technology significantly predicts their quality of education in Physics ($\beta = 14.6\%$). It was recommended among others that placement of students into science classes in senior secondary level should be strictly dependent on their achievement in Basic Science and Technology so as to guarantee acquisition of high quality science education at the senior secondary school. There should be a strong and reliable counseling unit in the schools with counselors to help handle the issue of placement in case any issue of interest arises either from the parent or student. Workshops, seminars and symposia should be organized regularly for science teachers to update their knowledge to enable them to teach Basic Science and Technology effectively thereby guarantees quality science education.

Key words: Students' achievement, Basic Science and Technology, and Quality Science Education.

Introduction

Education is perceived as an instrument for achievement of national objectives (FRN, 2008). The government is well aware that the technological advancement and social-economic development of any nation are dependent on educational development. Science education is the knowledge obtained from the systematic study of the structure and behaviour of the physical world, especially by observing, measuring and experimenting and

the development of theories to describe the results of these activities (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Basic Science and Technology is the bedrock on which the core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics at the senior secondary schools are laid. Basic Science and Technology as a subject come in existence as a result of curriculum reform movement in Nigeria to make science education more functional for sustainable national development.

The curriculum of Basic Science and Technology is a product of the restructuring and integration of four primary and junior secondary school science curricula namely; Basic Science, Basic Technology, Physical and Health Education and Computer Studies/Information Communication Technology (FRN, 2012). Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) (2012) posit that the need for integration of these science curricula became necessary for the following reasons: The recommendation of the presidential summit on education (2010) to reduce the number of subjects offered in primary and junior secondary schools; feedback from the implementation of the curricula in schools that identified repetition and duplication of concepts as the major cause of curriculum loaded; need to encourage innovative teaching and learning approaches and techniques that promotes creativity and critical thinking in learners; need to promote the holistic view of science at the Basic Education level for better understanding of contemporary and changing world and need to infuse emergent issues that are of national and global concern such as gender sensitivity, globalization and entrepreneurship.

Emphasis is therefore placed on it to give the students the right foundation for higher endeavour in science and technology. Nations that are considered to be developed and largely considered as civilized have achieved that status through purposeful scientific education of their citizens (Ajayi, 2017). In cognizance with the importance of science and technology, Basic Science and Technology are taught in Upper Basic schools in Nigeria to prepare a base for any science and technological development. Nigeria is looking forward to be among the most scientific and technologically advanced nations of the world. The reason is not far-fetched from numerous contributions of science and technology to human development (Ekundayo, 2012). For any nation, especially Nigeria, to achieve scientific and technologically advancement, it becomes imperative to start planning for a firm basic scientific education foundation for her citizens from childhood. This is because

children begin career exploration at a very young age. To move with this pace, Basic Science is taught at the primary school so as to catch the pupils' heart young. As a follow up, Basic Science and Technology is taught at the upper basic level to enable students to build up and concretize the knowledge of science they had at the primary school level and to lay the foundation for the study of the core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics at the senior secondary level of education.

In Nigeria, Basic Science and Technology is an important subject that is taught at the Upper Basic Education level while core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics are taught at the Senior Secondary level. Basic Science and Technology is one among science subjects which expresses the fundamental unity of scientific thought (Maduabum, 2011). It is expected that by teaching Basic Science and Technology to children at basic education level, every Nigerian student would be given the basic knowledge and understanding of what science is all about and some of the innovations that are taking place around them. This assertion blends with the objectives of science teaching at the Upper Basic Education which is to produce individuals who will be able to live effectively in the modern age of science and technology and contribute to the development of the nation (FRN, 2013).

Basic Science and Technology provides students at the upper basic education level with the initial theoretical and practical frameworks which are inevitable prerequisites for their future study. This statement buttressed by Ekundayo (2012) maintains that Basic Science and Technology enables students to understand science concepts, principles, theories and laws which are further elaborated in the core sciences such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics. It is regrettable that there is a public outcry due to poor quality science education, specifically in science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics. In this study, quality is defined as "fitness for purpose". Quality is considered as

“fitness for purpose”. Quality is considered as baseline standard in education. Quality therefore is an expression of standard or it is the means by which a certain set standard in education can be achieved. Quality science education is defined as the acquisition of measurable knowledge, skills, and attitudes among learners.

Although previous studies by Tytler (2012) and Scheerens (2013) agrees that science education quality can be determined by policy and contextual factors within the environment, the availability of inputs, the processes and the consumers of the products of science education. The present researchers also observes that, quality science education can also be determined by the students’ achievement in standardized examinations and since many teachers believe that the achievement of their students is an index of the quality of education acquired by the students. Poor quality science education is one the problems facing science and technology advancement in Nigeria in recent time. A good quality science education is one that provides all learners with capabilities they require to become economically productive, and develop sustainable livelihood, contributes to peaceful and democratic societies and to enhance individual well-being.

In this era of science and technology, Nigerians will need to be knowledgeable in science to prosper in a complex and global

society. Therefore, there is need to ensure inclusive and equitable quality science education. Quality improvement in science education encompasses the all-round development of learners in Basic science and technology at upper basic education level and in core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics respectively at senior secondary education level. Achieving high quality science education is difficult due to the fact that students lack important basic knowledge and skills of basic science and technology needed to be successful at the more advanced science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics at secondary school. By implication, poor achievement in Basic Science and Technology at upper basic education could invariably translate to poor quality science education, specifically in science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics at senior secondary schools. Thus, the study investigated if students’ achievement in Basic Science and Technology could predict quality science education.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated if students’ achievement in Basic Science and Technology could predict quality Science Education. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Ascertain if students’ achievement in Basic Science and Technology could predict their quality of education in Biology
2. Investigate if students’ achievement in Basic Science and Technology could predict their quality of education in Chemistry.
3. Determine if students’ achievement in Basic Science and Technology could predict their quality of education in Physics.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Biology?
2. What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Chemistry?
3. What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Physics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Biology.
2. Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Chemistry.
3. Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Physics.

Research Design and Procedure

Ex-post facto research design was used in this study. The independent (predictor) variable is the Basic Science and Technology scores in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) while the dependent (criterion) variable is the Biology, Chemistry and Physics scores in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE). The area of study is Zone B of Benue State, Nigeria. It has 54 schools offering both Basic Science and

core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics. These schools are owned by government, mission, single proprietors and community. The area comprises of seven local government areas namely; Makurdi, Tarka, Gboko, Buruku, Guma, Gwer and Gwer West Local Government Areas. Specifically, the study cuts across secondary schools in the seven local government areas found in the zone. The population of this study consisted of the results of students that graduated from 3-years Upper Basic Education (UBE) programme who offered Basic Science and Technology from the 54 schools in Zone B of Benue State between 2010-2014 and who also passed through 3-years Senior Secondary Education (SSE) who offered Biology, Chemistry and Physics between 2013-2017 respectively.

The sample of the study consisted of 327 Basic Science and Technology result in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) in the 2010/2011, 2011/2012, 2012/2013 and 2013/2014 academic sessions and their corresponding science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics results in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) for 2013/2014, 2014/2015, 2015/2016 and 2016/2017 academic sessions respectively were used. The technique was purposive sampling. This was because only those who offered Basic Science and Technology at Upper Basic, who in turn offered Science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics at Senior secondary, were sampled from the six sampled secondary schools within the area of study. Three upper basic schools that offered Basic Science and Technology at the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) and three senior secondary schools that offered Biology, Chemistry and Physics respectively at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE).

No instrument was developed. This is because the research is documentary and

No instrument was developed. This is because the research is documentary and so the researcher made use of students' records, which are their raw scores on those subjects needed for the study. In other words, the researcher used an inventory to collect the students' result scores (data). This became the instrument for the study. The results of students in BECE and SSCE used were administered by Benue State Examination Board and West African Examinations Council respectively provided the data for the study. Data collected were results of standard examinations already validated by the examination bodies in which the independent variables have already occurred and in which the researcher began with observation of a dependent variable, followed by a retrospective study possible relationship and effects. Regression analysis was used to

answer the research questions as well as to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. This method was considered appropriate to ascertain the strength of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables in the study

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and null hypotheses

Research Question One

What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Biology? The answer to research question one is contained on Table 1.

Table 1: Regression Analysis between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology and Quality of Education in Biology

Model	N	β (Reg. Weight)	R	Regression Square R^2
1	327	0.192	0.347	0.130

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The results in Table 1 show the regression analysis of the relationship between the students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Biology. The result implies that the independent variable has a positive regression weight. Accordingly, the measure of students' quality of education in Biology has 19.2% (or 0.192) regression weight. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.130. This implies that only 13.0% of the variation in students'

quality of education in Biology can be accounted for by their achievement in Basic Science and Technology.

Research Question Two

What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Chemistry? The answer to research question two is contained on Table 2.

Table 2: Regression Analysis between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology and Quality of Education in Chemistry

Model	N	β (Reg. Weight)	R	Regression Square R^2
1	327	0.157	0.330	0.122

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The results in Table 2 show the regression analysis of the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Chemistry. The analysis implies that the independent variable has a positive regression weight. Accordingly, the measure of students' quality of education in Physics has 15.7% (or 0.157) regression weight. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.122. This implies that only 12.2% of the variation in students'

quality of education in Chemistry can be attributed to achievement in Basic Science and Technology.

Research Question Three

What is the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Physics?

The answer to research question three is contained on Table 3.

Table 3: Regression Analysis between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology and Quality of Education in Physics

Model	N	β (Reg. Weight)	R	Regression Square R^2
1	327	0.146	0.221	0.102

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The results in Table 3 show the regression analysis of the relationship between students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Physics. The analysis implies that the independent variable has a positive regression weight. Accordingly, the measure of students' quality of education in Physics has 14.6% (or 0.146) regression weight. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.102. This implies that only 10.2% of the variation in students' quality of education in

Physics can be accounted for by their achievement in Basic Science and Technology.

Hypothesis One

Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Biology. The analysis of hypothesis one is contained on Table 4.

Table 4: ANOVA of Multiple Regression Relationship between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology and Quality of Education in Biology

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	37929.760	3	12806.861	62.111	.000 ^a
	Residual	158949.209	324	212.000		
	Total	196878.969	327			

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Analysis of data on Table 4 shows the ANOVA of multiple regression of relationship of students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Biology. The table revealed that, F value of

the predictor variable is 62.111, $P < 0.05$. Since $P < 0.05$ level of significance, it shows that students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Biology.

Thus, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This means that the students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Biology.

Hypothesis Two

Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Chemistry. The analysis of hypothesis two is contained on Table 5.

Table 5: ANOVA of Multiple Regression Relationship between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology and Quality of Education in Chemistry

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	29469.899	3	17502.091	33.009	.000 ^a
	Residual	132691.342	324	351.002		
	Total	162161.241	327			

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Analysis of data on Table 5 shows the ANOVA of multiple regression of relationship of male students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Chemistry. The table revealed that, F value of the predictor variable is 33.009, $P < 0.05$. Since $P < 0.05$ level of significance, it shows that students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Chemistry. Thus, the null hypothesis was

therefore rejected. This means that the students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Chemistry.

Hypothesis Three

Students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology does not significantly predict their quality of education in Physics. The analysis of hypothesis two is contained on Table 6.

Table 6: ANOVA of Multiple Regression Relationship between Students' Achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Physics and Quality of Education in Physics

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59960.092	3	22100.001	39.120	.000 ^a
	Residual	152908.061	324	271.900		
	Total	212868.153	327			

Analysis of data on Table 6 shows the ANOVA of multiple regression of relationship of students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology and their quality of education in Physics. The table revealed that, F value of the predictor variable is 39.120, $P < 0.05$. Since $P < 0.05$ level of significance, it shows that

students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Physics. Thus, the null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This means that the students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology significantly predict their quality of education in Physics.

Discussion

The main focus of this study was to investigate if students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology in Basic Education Certificate Examination is a predictor of quality education in Biology, Chemistry and Physics respectively in SSCE. The study also investigated the predictive power with reference to core science subjects such as Biology, Chemistry and Physics. The findings of the study show that low percentage of variation in the criterion variables can be attributed to the predictor variable. The study revealed that the students' quality of education in Biology has a predictive power. That is, students' academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology could be used to predict their quality of education in Biology. This means that students' academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology although could be used to predict their quality of education in Biology in SSCE might not be the sole determinant factor. This finding agrees with Abah (2013) and Adeipe (2015) who found that the knowledge of Basic Science and Technology provides solid foundation for the learning of chemistry concepts. In the same vein, the finding agrees with Oyedokun (2014) who revealed that students' performance in Integrated Science at junior secondary school is a predictor of achievement in Biology at senior secondary school level.

Another major finding of the study revealed that students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology in BECE predict their quality of education in Chemistry. This finding is in conformity with Bolarin (2011) and Owolabi (2012) who reported that students' achievement in chemistry in SSCE was low because of their low achievement in Basic Science and Technology at the upper basic school. The finding is contradictory to the reports of Ifamuyiwa (2014) who revealed that there is a significant relationship between the predictors and the criterion variables in science achievement.

In the same vein, the study revealed that students' achievement in Basic Science and Technology in BECE predict their quality of education in Physics. The study revealed that the students' quality of education in Physics has a predictive power. That is, students' academic achievement in Basic Science and Technology could be used to predict their quality of education in Physics. The finding agrees with Achor (2003) who examined the relationship between measures of students' field independency, cognitive tasks, formal reasoning and their achievement in Physics.

The implication of this result is that students who performed well in Basic Science and Technology would likely maintain the same level of achievement if their interest is sustained in the study of the core science subjects (Biology, Chemistry and Physics).

This might be possible if other factors such as qualified and committed science teachers use appropriate instructional materials to present science concepts to them, otherwise there would be changes in the performance. With these positive relationships which exist between the students achievement in Basic Science and Technology and quality of science education, someone can conclude that when a student enters each new learning task, with a particular history of previous learning, it will determine the nature of the candidate's interaction with the new learning task and the learning outcomes of that interaction.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It is evident from the findings of this study that the achievement in Basic Science and Technology in BECE has significant predictive power on the students' quality of science education at senior secondary school level. The study has provided further insight into the process of allocating class to students after their junior secondary education. This implies that the rigidity associated with the allocation of students to class or field of study based on BECE results should be upheld. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that achievement of students in Basic Science and Technology is a predictor of their quality of science education in Education.

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations are made: Placement of students into science classes in senior secondary level should be strictly dependent on their achievement in Basic Science and Technology so as to guarantee acquisition of high quality science education at the senior secondary school. There should be a strong and reliable counseling unit in the schools with counselors to help handle the issue of placement in case any issue of interest arises either from the parent or student. Workshops, seminars and symposia should be organized regularly for science teachers to update their knowledge to enable them to teach Basic Science and Technology effectively and guarantee quality science education.

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